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Abstract book

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PSEUDOEXFOLIATION GLAUCOMA FREQUENCY AND PRESENTING FEATURES IN PATIENTS REFERRED TO A TERTIARY OPHTHALMOLOGY CLINIC IN SERBIA

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Background: Pseudoexfoliation (PEX) syndrome is not only an ocular disease but also a general disorder that involves the abnormal production and disposal of extracellular matrix material in intra- and extraocular tissues. Intraocular pressure (IOP) of the pseudoexfoliative eyes is higher than IOP of the non-pseudoexfoliative eyes which leads to more severe eye damage during longer period of time. Glaucoma in the pseudoexfoliation syndrome has been shown to have a more serious clinical course than in primary open-angle glaucoma.

Aim: The aim of our study was to determine the presence and frequency of pseudoexfoliation (capsular) glaucoma compared to other types of glaucoma among patients examined in one month period and in total number of glaucoma operated patients during last year.

Material and methods: Our study involved 105 patients examined and diagnosed in November 2016 and 346 glaucoma patients operated between January and October 2016 at Clinic for eye diseases, Clinical Centre of Serbia. Methods used in examination and monitoring of patients were: biomicroscopy, applanation tonometry, computerized perimetry, ophthalmoscopy, gonioscopy and Heidelberg Retinal Tomography II (HRT II).

Results: Although the frequency of capsular glaucoma in our sample was more common in women 14 (13.4%) compared to men 11 (10.4%), statistically significant difference related to sex was not observed. Binocular expression was 3.7 times more often than monocular in women and 1.7 times in men. Among glaucoma operated patients, capsular glaucoma was found in 94 (27.2%) cases, which indicates that every fourth patient operated last year had this type of glaucoma.

Conclusion: Based on the results of our study, it can be concluded that in patients with capsular glaucoma, early detection and monitoring of pseudoexfoliation in the eye is extremely important for undertaking an adequate therapeutic procedure on time and better long-term prognosis.

Key words: PEX syndrome; glaucoma; frequency; diagnosis